

EVOLVE2CARE

Engaging the Value of Living Labs to Innovate Care and Regulatory Environments

Project Brand Book

ViLabs (CY) LTD | Vassilis Voulgarakis
Contact info: vmvoulga@vilabs.eu

Funded by
the European Union

Executive Summary

The purpose of this brand book is to assist the Consortium in using the EVOLVE2CARE logo appropriately.

It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and others assigned with the production of branded items to design and create EVOLVE2CARE communication materials in an adequate manner.

In order to maintain the integrity of the visual identity of the project it is important to apply all the elements of the present guide properly and consistently.

Contents

1. Project Logo

- Primary version
- Negative version
- Instructions

2. Project colours

3. Typography

- Font Family
- Text formats and configurations

Project Logo (primary version)

The logo of the EVOLVE2CARE acts as the project's first connection with the audiences, and it is considered the cornerstone of a coherent visual identity to trademark the partners' work in any electronic and/or print outputs. It consists of the project emblem and the project acronym:

The logo should be used mainly on a white (i.e., bright and simple) background in its primary version for maximum impact and clarity.

Project Logo (negative version)

In cases of coloured and/or patterned backgrounds, the negative version of the project logo should be used to maintain contrast levels, thus ensuring proper visibility:

Instructions

Clear space surrounding the project logo should remain free of competing texts, logos, images or any other visual element that could interfere with the logo. The indicative space should be set at approximately $\frac{1}{2}x$ of the logo dimensions.

Instructions

The display of the project logo should comply with the versions that are specified in this guide. The logo may not appear in any other colours and versions than the predefined.

The logo should not be altered in any shape or format or even combined with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

Colour scheme

The EVOLVE2CARE colour scheme is the following:

- Primary Colour: #366087 [Lapis Lazuli]
 - Secondary Colour 1: # 65A5D3 [Air Superiority Blue]
 - Secondary Colour 2: # 95D3EA [Sky Blue]
 - Secondary Colour 3: #E2FDFF [Light Cyan]
 - Extra Colour 1: #57C3A6 [Mint]
 - Extra Colour 2: #C5DCA0 [Tea Green]

Important note:

CMYK colors are used in **printing materials**, while **RGB colors** are used on **web applications**.

Font Family

The project uses two specific fonts:

- Poppins (for Headings and titles)
- Open Sans (for normal text, subtitles and captions)

These two fonts must be opted for all communication materials, online and print , as well as in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the project website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given fonts should be avoided.

Poppins (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Poppins (Bold)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Poppins (Italic)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
*1234567890!@#&%**

Open Sans (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Open Sans (Bold)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Open Sans (Italic)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
*1234567890!@#&%**

Text formats and configurations

Text Format	Configurations				
	Font	Size	Style	Colour	Alignment
Heading 1	Poppins	24	Normal	#366087	Justified
Heading 2	Poppins	18	Normal	#366087	Justified
Heading 3	Poppins	14	Normal	#366087	Justified
Heading 4	Poppins	12	Normal	#366087	Justified
Normal Text	Open Sans	12	Normal	#000000	Justified
Captions	Open Sans	11	Italics	#366087	Centered